

Mortality from Road Accidents in the Italian Regions

It decreased on average of 65.27% between 2004 and 2019

The Istat-Bes calculates the value of mortality from road accidents defined as a mortality rate from foreign accidents within the age of 15-34 years.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of the mortality rate for road accidents. Veneto is in the first place for mortality rate from road accidents with a value equal to 1, followed by Puglia, Calabria, Sicily with a value of 0.8. The Lombardy, Marche and Abruzzo ranking close with a value of 0.5, followed by Basilicata with 0.3 and by the Aosta Valley with a value of 0. On average in 2019 the value of mortality from road accidents was equal to an amount of 0.62 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage variation of the mortality index for road accidents between 2004 and 2019. The Aosta Valley is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the mortality index for road accidents with a value equal to -100.00% equal to a value of -1.80 units, followed by Abruzzo with a value equal to -77.27% equal to an amount of -1.70 units and from Basilicata with a value equal to -75, 00% equal to an amount of 0.90 units. In the middle of the standings there are Trentino -Alto Adige with a value equal to -69.57% equal to an amount of -1.60 units, followed by Piedmont and Friuli -Venezia Giulia with a value equal to -65.00% equal to an amount of -1.30 units. Campania close the ranking with a value equal to -45.45% equal to an amount of -0.50 units, followed by Sicily with a value equal to -42.86% equal to an amount of -0.60 units e From Calabria with a variation of -33.33% equal to an amount of -0.40 units.

Italian macro-regions. The value of mortality from road accidents in Italian macro-regions has significantly decreased between 2004 and 2019. In northern Italy, mortality from road accidents decreased from a value of 2 units up to a value of 0.7 units or even to a variation of -1.30 units equal to a value of -65.00%. In Central Italy, mortality from road accidents has decreased from a value of 2 units up to a value of 0.6 units or equal to a variation of -1.40 units equal to -70.00%. In the South of Italy, mortality from road accidents decreased from a value of 1.5 units up to a value of 0.7 units or equal to a variation of -0.80 units equal to a value of -53.33% Overall, in Italy the mortality from road accidents has decreased from an amount of 1.8 units up to a value of 0.7 units or equal to a variation of -1.10 units equal to a variation of -61.11%.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm. Below is a clusterization using the K-means algorithm optimized through the silhouette coefficient. The identified optimal cluster number is 2 as indicated below or:

- *Cluster 1:* Campania, Calabria, Molise, Basilicata, Liguria, Sicily, Trentino-Alto Adige, Lombardy;
- *Cluster 2:* Veneto, Lazio, Emilia-Romagna, Piedmont, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Puglia, Umbria, Puglia, Marche, Abruzzo, Tuscany, Sardinia;
- *Cluster 3:* Valle d'Aosta.

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, European Union. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it

Considering the median of the value of the Clusters appears that the value of the median of the variable observed in the regions of the 1-C1 cluster is equal to 0.65, the median of the Cluster 2-C2 is 0.7, the median of the 3- C3 is equal to 0. Therefore, the following system derives or: $C2 = 0.7 > C1 = 0.65 > C3 = 0$. From a geographical point of view, it is not possible to find a contrast between Italian macro-regions as the regions of C2 are distributed in the South, in the center and northern Italy.

Machine learning and predictions. Eight different Machine Learning algorithms are compared for the prediction of the future value of mortality from road accidents in the Italian regions. The algorithms were trained with 70% of the available data, while the remaining 30% was used for prediction. The performance of the algorithms was compared using a set of indicators or R-squared, Mean Absolute Error, Mean Squared Error, Root Mean Squared Error. The results show the following system for predictive capacity or:

- Tree Regression Ensemble with a payoff value of 5;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 9;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 10;
- Gradient Boosted Tree Regression with a payoff value of 16;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 22;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 24;
- Random Forest Regression and Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 29.

The following predictions have been made below by applying the Tree Ensemble Regression Algorithm:

- Liguria with a diminutive variation from an amount of 0.70 units up to a value of 0.61 units or equal to a variation of -0.09 units equal to -12.86%;
- Friuli Venezia Giulia with a diminutive variation from an amount of 0.70 units up to a value of 0.66 units equal to an amount of -0.04 units equal to -5.14%;
- Tuscany with an increased variation from an amount of 0.60 units up to a value of 0.64 units or equal to a variation of 0.04 units equal to an amount of 6.17%;
- Umbria with an increased variation from a value of 0.60 units up to a value of 0.65 units or equal to a variation of 0.05 units equal to an amount of 8.33%;
- Puglia with a diminutive variation from an amount of 0.80 units up to a value of 0.68 units or equal to an absolute variation of -0.12 units equal to a variation of -14.88%;
- Sardinia with a diminutive variation from an amount of 0.70 units up to a value of 0.61 units or equal to a variation of -0.09 units equal to an amount of -12.43%.

On average, the value of the variation is envisaged in decrease for the regions considered by an amount of 0.68 units up to a value of 0.64 units or equal to -0.04 units equal to -5.98%.

Conclusions. Mortality from road accidents has decreased in all Italian regions between 2004 and 2019. This reductive trend should also continue in the future especially following the creation of a better road network and in application of new safety tools on board cars that can prevent accidents by acting as a life -saving.

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Appendinx

Variazione percentuale della mortalità per incidenti stradali tra il 2004 ed il 2019			
Rank	Regione	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	★ -1,80	★ -100,00
2	Abruzzo	★ -1,70	★ -77,27
3	Basilicata	★ -0,90	★ -75,00
4	Emilia-Romagna	★ -2,00	★ -74,07
5	Toscana	★ -1,50	★ -71,43
6	Lombardia	★ -1,20	★ -70,59
7	Marche	★ -1,20	★ -70,59
8	Lazio	★ -1,40	★ -70,00
9	Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	★ -1,60	★ -69,57
10	Piemonte	★ -1,30	★ -65,00
11	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ -1,30	★ -65,00
12	Umbria	★ -1,10	★ -64,71
13	Liguria	★ -1,00	★ -58,82
14	Sardegna	★ -1,00	★ -58,82
15	Puglia	★ -1,10	★ -57,89
16	Veneto	★ -1,20	★ -54,55
17	Molise	★ -0,50	★ -45,45
18	Campania	★ -0,50	★ -45,45
19	Sicilia	★ -0,60	★ -42,86
20	Calabria	★ -0,40	★ -33,33

Clusterizzazione. Mortalità per Incidenti Stradali nel 2019. $C2 > C1 > C0$.

	2019	Regioni	Cluster
13	0.5	Abruzzo	C2
17	0.3	Basilicata	C1
18	0.8	Calabria	C1
15	0.6	Campania	C1
8	0.7	Emilia-Romagna	C2
7	0.7	Friuli-Venezia G...	C2
12	0.6	Lazio	C2
3	0.7	Liguria	C1
4	0.5	Lombardia	C1
11	0.5	Marche	C2
14	0.6	Molise	C1
1	0.7	Piemonte	C2
16	0.8	Puglia	C2
20	0.7	Sardegna	C2
19	0.8	Sicilia	C1
9	0.6	Toscana	C2
5	0.7	Trentino-Alto A...	C1
10	0.6	Umbria	C2
2	0.0	Valle d'Aosta/V...	C3
6	1.0	Veneto	C2

